

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF 3D-PRINTED CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC LOOPED TENSILE ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The strength of novel 3D-printed (by a process called layer-wise Fused Filament Deposition [FFD]) pin-loaded looped tensile structural elements made from unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP), these being small-scale models for bridge deck suspender cables of network arch bridges, was investigated. The straps were printed from continuous carbon fiber reinforced filaments (AS4 fiber in a polyamide 12 matrix) and subsequently stretched and compacted under pressure at 200°C in order to reduce porosity under 1% and to diminish fiber waviness. This paper presents the tensile strength and tensile fatigue performance of the 3D-printed CFRP straps that were loaded over two titanium pins of 20 mm diameter.

KEYWORDS: CFRP; looped tensile elements; 3D-printing; tensile fatigue

INTRODUCTION

Steel as the conventional material used for tensile elements in railway bridges has well-known durability and fatigue limitations (Baschnagel et al., 2016). The five times lighter CFRP is becoming a more and more important tensile load-bearing material in the construction and structural repair industry, due to very light weight and its outstanding mechanical properties including the excellent fatigue resistance. This last property enabled the first large (127 m span) bridge fully relying on pretensioned CFRP looped strap elements which is a network arch bridge opened December 2021 in Stuttgart (Germany) over the A8 motorway (Meier et al., 2021), where the bridge deck is hanging entirely on 72 CFRP hangers. The superior fatigue endurance limit of the 33 mm diameter pin-loaded CFRP strap hangers (Carbo-Link, 2023; Baschnagel et al., 2018) is around 6-times higher than for flat-steel hangers according to Eurocode 3 (EN 1993-1-9 (2005)). Due to the very low weight of the hangers, they could be installed manually by two persons with the aid of a light mobile platform. Moreover, the construction was cheaper than with the originally planned conventional network arch bridge with flat steel hangers (which are limited in fatigue strength, need corrosion protection and sometimes balancing weights to keep hangers tensioned to avoid them becoming slack). The Stuttgart network arch bridge was ground breaking due to the exclusive use of CFRP tensile elements: These hangers were made of Out Of Autoclave [OOA] carbon fiber epoxy prepregs in an automated tape-laying machine with subsequent heat-supported curing by the Empa spin-off company Carbo-Link AG (Carbo-Link, 2023; Meier et al., 2020), a laborious process which motivated Empa to evaluate other possibilities of manufacturing the straps. Moreover, as the prestressed CFRP hangers are subjected to high tensile fatigue loads, a better understanding of the fatigue behavior of the 3D printed CFRP straps in combination with the inevitable fretting at their titanium pin-attachments is of paramount importance and motivated this research project.

Several types of CFRP straps are possible, which can be conventionally produced with either lamination, pultrusion, tape-winding (Meier et al., 2020) or pullwinding (Yue et al., 2015). Within this project, the tension straps (or pin-loaded looped hanger models in small-scale) were manufactured by layer-wise Fused Filament Deposition (3D printing) of continuous unidirectional CFRP filaments that were then additionally compacted in a mold before being tested for quasi static tensile strength and under accelerated cyclic loading at 10 Hz. 3D printing CFRP is a relatively new approach to composite manufacturing, and has been a topic in research and development in the past five years. However, based on a recent literature review performed by Sanei and Popescu (Sanei and Popescu, 2020), this technique needs to be thoroughly investigated, especially with respect to fatigue resistance

due to the risk of manufacturing flaws like increased porosity, fiber waviness and misalignments. By implementing a 3D printing process for CFRP, the production flexibility is increased by continuously changing the direction of the fibers through the part with a theoretically precise and repeatable fiber deposition without needing a complex mold. There are many different approaches to 3D printing CFRP, from using chopped to continuous fibers, and by implementing matrix either before the print (as in pre-impregnated filament CFRP), or introducing the matrix while printing, again either in the extrusion head or at the printing platform itself. After production of the part by 3D printing, post processing of the preform is required. This is essentially a compression of the preform at an elevated temperature (slightly over the melting temperature of the thermoplastic matrix polymer) to achieve the final geometry while minimizing porosity and therewith increasing the mechanical properties of the part (see e.g. Hagenauer et al., 2020). For the model looped CFRP straps studied in this research (Figure 1 bottom right), quasi-static tensile properties were investigated and a tensile fatigue testing campaign ($R=0.1$ and frequency = 10 Hz) was completed in order to derive an S-N curve, which is an important design tool for tensile elements in railway bridges. The results were compared with the tensile and fatigue performance of conventional carbon fiber reinforced epoxy straps laminated by tape laying using OOA prepreps published previously by Empa (Baschnagel et al., 2016 and 2018). Similar full-scale straps were implemented by the Empa-spin-off company Carbo-Link in the first network arch bridge for a railway in Stuttgart Germany opened in December 2021 (Meier et al., 2021). This study concludes that the fused filament fabrication process and the thermoplastic CFRP straps have the potential to compete with classical CFRP straps produced by tape laying and sheds light on the necessary future research in order to improve the performance and processing of additively manufactured CFRP looped tensile elements.

PROCESSING OF SAMPLES

For the fabrication of the 3D printed specimens the authors developed a stable and reliable printing process and post-processing step (described by Vidrih, 2021). Then manufacturing and testing of the straps was performed according to Figure 1.

Figure 1: Fabrication procedure of 3D-printed CFRP straps with post-compaction mould assembly.

The looped strap specimens were 3D printed with one continuous (looped) motion using a 9T Labs (2021) fused filament printer (Figure 1 section 1 - 3d Printer make: Ultimaker 2+, with additional Carbon Kit unit by 9T Labs), and no cutting of the fibres was necessary. The filament used was an AS4 carbon fiber PA12 filament with 60% nominal fiber volume amount supplied by 9T Labs (Zurich). The printing parameters used were:

- Carbon fiber nozzle temperature: 200 °C
- Platform / bed temperature: 90 °C
- Nozzle diameter: 0.8 mm
- Layer height: 0.23 mm
- Nr. of perimeters: 1
- Printing speed: 4 mm/s

The filament properties given by the supplier 9T Labs (Zurich) are given in Figure 2.

Composite Filament		
Carbon Fiber: AS4		
Fiber Volume Content: 60%		
	Value	Test method
Density (g/cm ³)	1.48	-
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	100	ISO 527
Tensile Strength (MPa)	1750	ISO 527
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	95	ISO 14125
Flexural Strength (MPa)	900	ISO 14125
In-plane Shear Modulus (GPa)	1.4	ISO 14129
In-plane Shear Strength (MPa)	45	ISO 14129
T _g (°C)	40	DSC
T _m (°C)	178	DSC

Figure 2: Carbon fiber AS4 reinforced PA12 filament properties (9T Labs, 2021)

The as printed model dimensions of the looped strap specimens were on average 218.5 mm (length) x 24 mm (outer diameter of the loop/end curvature) x 1.3 mm (thickness) x 20 mm (width). Since the design of the strap involves two 180° curves at their curved ends, some waviness of the fibre was present in the preform at its curvatures. These areas are controlling the tensile strength when the straps is subjected to tension (Schürmann, 2007) and needed to be improved by a post-processing step: Stretching of the fibres was therefore necessary. This was achieved in the post-processing step with a specially designed mould (See Figure 1 section 2-6) that was able to apply tensile forces from inside the strap to straighten up the fibres in particular in their crucial curvature area. The 3D printed preform was placed into the mould cavity and then heated up in a hydraulic press (Figure 1 section 5-6). Because the mould includes independently driven wedge and stamp, it was possible to apply the force separately to the wedge, which drove the two mould halves horizontally and therefore stretched the fibres (see Figure 1, section 4). When the level of the wedge reached alignment with the stamp, additional pressure was applied vertically and compression of the specimen was performed in its width direction. This principle allowed obtaining unidirectionally fiber reinforced tension straps manufactured from one continuous CFRP strand, with rather straight fibres and low void content (below 1.3%, determined by optical analysis of polished cross sections via the software the ImageJ (ImageJ, 2018)). The above post processing mould was specially designed to achieve a given final strap geometry (given in Table 1) of 20 mm inner diameter of the curved ends x 10.75 mm width x 222.6 mm length and a strap thickness of 1.3 mm on average. In order to achieve these dimensions a set of preliminary tests was performed by printing straps with variable length and curvature diameter and by and observing fiber waviness at the looped ends after compression (macroscopically and under the optical microscope).

The final dimensions of six consolidated straps (the ones then tested in quasi-static tension) are given exemplary in Table 1: Therefore the elongation of the straps after post processing (and stretching) was on average 4.1 mm. Their final inner diameter at the looped ends was 20.0 mm, as stated above.

Despite the rather laborious post-printing compaction with the axial strap stretching and compression in the width direction some fiber waviness was observed when performing optical microscopy of the strap cross-sections, see Figure 3 (a) for the thickness direction and (b) for the axial direction. This clearly influenced the quasi-static tensile performance and the tensile fatigue results described in the following chapters and shows that the process can be improved in future research.

Tension strap	Height [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Cross-section area [mm ²]	Length [mm]	F _{max} [N]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Elastic Modulus [GPa]
CFRPA12-18	11,32	1,33	30,11	222,55	42477	1410,67	-
CFRPA12-19	10,98	1,30	28,55	222,62	41523	1454,50	-
CFRPA12-20	10,67	1,31	27,96	222,58	34942	1249,92	131,88
CFRPA12-21	10,61	1,31	27,80	222,59	32499	1169,10	135,75
CFRPA12-22	9,90	1,31	25,94	222,51	38129	1470,01	130,95
CFRPA12-23	11,01	1,30	28,54	222,75	32306	1132,04	130,54
St. deviation	0,49	0,01	1,36	0,082	4837,50	149,42	2,38
Average	10,75	1,31	28,15	222,60	36979,33	1314,37	132,28

Table 1: Final dimensions of the post processed 3D printed straps no. 18-22 (then tested in quasi-static tension to failure)

Figure 3: Fibre waviness in thickness direction (a) and in printing direction (b)

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The ultimate tensile strength tests were performed on five coupons prepared by printing flat plates by FFD (Vidrih, 2021), six non compressed and six compressed (i.e. post-processed) CFRP straps (Figure 4). All tests were conducted on a servo-hydraulic test machine of type Instron 1251. All tensile tests were carried out in quasi-static conditions, with cross-head speed of 2mm/min. The loads were introduced with an adaptor that fixed the strap's ends using Ti64 bolts of diameter 20 mm (Figure 4-2b). Fibre parallel strains were measured on the compressed tension straps with a linear encoder with a measuring length of 50mm. Strain measurements however were not possible on the 3D printed uncompressed preforms, as their tensile capacity was quite low and their scatter rather high, such as the unpredictable failure could damage the strain encoder. Additionally a series of tensile fatigue tests was performed on the compressed straps only at a frequency of 10 Hz and R=0.1 for 28 additional tension straps and various loads. Specimens were exposed to upper tensile stress levels between 500 and 900 MPa until failure. The specimens that did not fail in fatigue after 3-9 million load cycles were tested for their residual tensile strength following the above testing procedure.

Figure 4: Experimental set-up for static and dynamic testing of the 3D-printed CFRP tension straps

RESULTS

The non-compressed tension straps (i.e. straps that did not undergo the above described post processing procedure of Figure 1) failed prematurely at low loading (Figure 4), due to the rather bad compaction and adhesion between the layers, fiber misalignment, low interlaminar strength (this was not measured but the fused filaments were showing macroscopical pores at their contact surface to the next filament) and high void content (over 8%). As explained above a strain encoder was not installed during the tensile tests, and the elastic modulus of an uncompressed 3D printed strap preform could therefore not be determined.

The values of tensile strength for the post processed straps were all between 1100-1470 MPa, with an average of 1314.4 MPa and a COV of 11.4% (Table 1 and Figure 5, the high COV being an indication that the 3D-printing process and proposed post-processing can be improved). Tensile strength is much lower (60.8%) compared to that of a flat coupon specimen of the same AS4 carbon fibers in PA matrix that gave an average of 2163 MPa (COV = 6.2%, see Vidrih, 2021). The cause for the lower performance of tensile strap is due to its shape, since the load transfer capacity is diminished by the stress concentrations in the vertex area of the strap (Winistörfer, 1999; Schürmann, 2007). The elastic elongation of the strap that occurs during the tensile loading causes the curved area of the strap to shift along the pin and yet retain its curvature. This phenomenon induces a bending moment in the vertex area, which causes stress concentrations and reduces the mechanical performance of the tension strap compared to the material properties (Baschnagel et al., 2016). The average value of the strap's elastic modulus is 132.28 GPa (COV = 1.8%), which coincides with the material datasheet value of the AS4 PA filament used (9T Labs, 2021).

Figure 5: Tensile tests of consolidated vs. non-consolidated straps. The measured average ultimate tensile strength of the corresponding UD coupons was 2163 MPa (COV = 6.2%)

Finally, 28 tension straps were tested in tensile fatigue at 10 Hz and $R = 0.1$. The results can be seen in the Figure 6. In the failed samples fretting fatigue at their attachments over the titanium pins was predominant and determined failure (Vidrih, 2021) but the temperatures measured on the strap surface of all fatigued (at 10 HZ) specimens were lower than 60°C ($< T_G = 180^{\circ}\text{C}$ of the PA12 matrix). Three samples loaded with a tensile stress amplitude of 450 MPa at a frequency of 10Hz, were able to withstand $3 \cdot 10^6$ (then halted) and four samples under the same conditions were able to sustain $9 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles without failure (see the runout specimens in Figure 5 all with $\Delta\sigma = 450$ MPa at $R = 0.1$). The fatigue endurance limit (meant as upper stress level for $R = 0.1$ and 10 Hz testing frequency) was therefore determined to be 500 MPa and corresponds to 38% of the CFRP straps' ultimate tensile strength of 1314 MPa. As a comparison, CFRP model straps with exactly the same geometry with a stronger carbon IMS60 fibre that were conventionally produced with out-of-autoclave process, have their fatigue endurance limit of 750 MPa, which corresponds to 46% of their ultimate tensile strength (Baschnagel et al., 2016). The seven specimens that did not fail in fatigue were additionally tested for their residual tensile strength, which lead to values of 1129 MPa after 3 million load cycles and 1244 MPa after 9 million load cycles. These results on the fatigue performance look promising, and further research will focus on the improvement of the manufacturing process of the strap and mould design in order to reduce porosity and fibre waviness (Figure 3). With further optimization of the mould design, the impregnation and fiber orientation and therefore the overall performance of the CFRP strap can be additionally enhanced. In the interest of exploiting the advantages of the presented additive manufacturing process, a further analysis focussing on the topological optimization of the tension strap at its looped ends will follow.

Figure 6: Fatigue curve (Stress amplitude range vs. Number of cycles) for 3D-printed CFRP straps

CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this study show a good potential for further research on 3D printed CFRP straps under the assumption of an appropriate compaction procedure post printing. A fatigue endurance limit for the thermoplastic matrix straps of 500 MPa (i.e. $\Delta\sigma_{\text{end}} = 450$ MPa at $R = 0.1$) could be determined for a testing frequency of 10 Hz. This corresponds to 38% of their average quasi-static tensile strength of the CFRP straps. As a comparison, straps made with a stronger IMS60 carbon fiber that were conventionally produced with an out-of-autoclave process (epoxy matrix), have their fatigue endurance limit of 750 MPa, which corresponds to 46% of their ultimate tensile strength under same R-ratio and testing frequency of 10 Hz (Baschnagel et al., 2016).

The main limitation of the processing method presented in this paper is the necessary and laborious post-processing after 3D printing (FFF) of the CFRP straps. This includes an axial stretching followed by a transversal post-compaction in a complex and expensive steel mold. This tool needs to be designed and produced for each strap geometry in a practical application, e.g. for network arch bridge strap-hangers of diameter 33 mm and lengths of several meters. This is a clear limitation of the 3D printing technique by FFF of thermoplastic matrix straps as it makes the strap production expensive and inflexible. It therefore greatly compromises the advantages (geometric freedom, fast production) of printing CFRP laminates with thermoplastic-matrix. The development of a heated compaction roller unit just after filament deposition as described by (Ueda et al., 2020) could be a solution to this technological problem for simpler 3D-printed geometries and components.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.